

Deliverable D8.3

Report on interactions with other organizations, projects and the IAB (1|2)

Deliverable report

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DigiEcoQuarry project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as consequence of project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DigiEcoQuarry technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allows a close follow up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

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List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
DoA	Description of Action
D	Deliverable
EASME	Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
EB	Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
EURMKB	European Raw Materials Knowledge Base
GA	Grant Agreement
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IAB	International Advisory Board
IFS	Individual Financial Statement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
PFSIGN	Project Financial Statement
PRC	Project Research Committee
RMIS	Raw Materials Information System
RMKG	Raw Materials Knowledge Gateway
RP	Reporting Period
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

This document (Deliverable 8.3) contains a comprehensive report on the clustering activities conducted in the first 24 months of DigiEcoQuarry Project (up to May 31, 2023) with regard to the interactions with other organizations, projects and the International Advisory Board (IAB). Most of the activities carried out were foreseen in the initial document: Deliverable 8.1 'Clustering Plan of the DigiEcoQuarry project', with some extensions or refinements where necessary. It presents the collective effort of the consortium on the project's clustering activities and summarizes all the recorded results of the ongoing monitoring.

This deliverable corresponds to the Task 8.1 of Work Package (WP) 8 'Clustering activities for a solid EU knowledge base on raw materials'. The Clustering Plan was revised yearly, with ad hoc revisions made according to the progress of the project. In this regard, another report on interactions with other organizations, projects and the International Advisory Board will be published by the end of the project, in May 2025.

The Project INNOVATIVE DIGITAL SUSTAINABLE AGGREGATES SYSTEMS (H2020-SC5-2020-2) is exploiting the aggregates industry's great potential through a coordinated approach towards construction materials management with the final goal of reducing EU external supply dependency as well as leading to an efficient use of resources. DigiEcoQuarry is developing systems, technology and processes for integrated digitization and automation real-time process control, to be piloted in 5 EU quarries with the target of improving health and safety conditions for workers. The pilot campaigns will lead to improved efficiency of processes maximizing quarry resources and sustainable management of water, energy emissions, minimized environmental impact and expanding the EU aggregates and construction business. Coupling Artificial Intelligence approaches with cyber-physical systems and the Internet of Things concept, make Industry 4.0 approach possible and the smart sustainable extractive site a reality. All phases of the process, from extraction to the end user are covered by DigiEcoQuarry, ensuring communication with policy makers, social acceptance activities and international cooperation with the Colombia and South Africa partners to share knowledge and best practices. The development of an innovative Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) will increase the sustainable supply of minerals for the construction sector as well as enabling the sustainable extraction of EU's mineral resources in existing and new quarries.

This Project includes 25 partners and will last for 48 months, starting on 1st June 2021. It is divided into 11 Work Packages. One of them is Work Package 8 (WP8), named Clustering activities for a solid EU knowledge base on raw materials, which is covering the complete duration of the Project.

The main objective of WP8 is to conduct clustering activities to **ensure transfer of knowledge and cooperation** among the relevant stakeholders, also feeding results from the pilots into the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) and European Raw Materials Knowledge Base (EURMKB) databases.

WP8 is working to establish a powerful and solid network of key stakeholders and end users with potential interest in the project's successful execution and results that will expand the project's scope towards new market opportunities to maximize its impact. Specifically, the main goals of WP8 are: (1) Define a Clustering plan to build progressively a collaborative network, consolidating the presence of the consortium partners in clusters and other relevant platforms; (2) Ensure transfer of knowledge and cooperation among the relevant stakeholders, also feeding results and findings from the pilots into the RMIS and EURMKB databases; and (3) Organize an International Advisory Board composed of relevant stakeholders of the aggregates value chain to provide external input, advice and feedback when the project is experiencing difficulties during its execution.

2 Introduction and scope

The present deliverable ‘**D8.3: Report on interactions with other organizations, projects and the IAB**’ is prepared in the context of Work Package 8, named “Clustering activities for a solid EU knowledge base on raw materials” and it is associated with the work being done within tasks T8.1 “Networking and Clustering”, T8.2 “Cooperation with RMIS and EURMKB databases” and T8.3 “Interaction with the International Advisory Board”.

This deliverable should be viewed as the next instalment of Deliverables D8.1 “Clustering Plan of the DigiEcoQuarry project”, and D8.2 “Protocols to cooperate with RMIS and EURMKB”, in the context that here we report on the implementation of the strategies defined in D8.1 and D8.2 and compliments the original planning and charts a new course where required. Although we commented on the activities performed during the Reporting Period 1, D8.3 is the first report covering DigiEcoQuarry’s clustering progress and status at midterm, while a second version, namely D8.4, is scheduled for release at the end of the project. As commented, D8.1 is continuously evaluated and updated throughout the project’s lifetime and revised at every project meeting, if deemed necessary. As such, it needs to be seen as a “living” document, with revisions throughout the duration of the project.

The carefully targeted clustering strategy defined in the beginning of the project has been followed to maximise the impact of the project together with activities performed within Work Package 9 (Dissemination, communication and exploitation). The identified target groups and key stakeholders along with the dissemination mechanisms and clear objectives were instrumental for planning and executing the activities that took place on the first 24 months of the project and are included in this report. In fact, monthly meetings were organized with the leaders of WP9 and WP7 (Fig. 1). Thus, WP8 is working very close to WP7 and, especially, WP9 to establish a powerful and solid network of key stakeholders and end users with potential interest in the project’s successful execution and results that will expand the project’s scope towards new market opportunities to maximize its impact.

Figure 1 Relationship between WPs 7, 8 and 9.

As stated in **D8.1**, the **Clustering Plan** aimed to design the strategy, plan and activities to be implemented under the DigiEcoQuarry project, with a view to build progressively a collaborative network, consolidating the presence of the consortium partners in clusters and other relevant platforms.

In this regard, the consortium is trying to build up a solid and self-sufficient international contact network around the project. The partners are working to consolidate their presence and rallying up additional support from the following areas: (1) Quarry-related organizations, platforms, and clusters (European, International & national) linked to the 25 partners (to increase this, the European Cluster Collaboration Platform and the EIT Raw Materials will also be followed); and (2) Relevant projects and initiatives.

DigiEcoQuarry partners were committed to ensure the transfer of knowledge and cooperation (in line with EURMKB and RMIS), facilitating the sharing of information and results from the pilots to be discussed and analysed with the target audiences. Thus, diverse initiatives were defined in D8.1 and D8.2.

2.1 Structure of the deliverable

With the above in mind, the “Report on interactions with other organizations, projects and the IAB” is structured as follows:

Section 1 - Executive summary: Contains a brief statement of Deliverable 8.3.

Section 2 – Introduction and scope: Provides introductory information with respect to the Clustering Plan (Deliverable 8.1) and the Protocols to cooperate with RMIS and EURMKB (Deliverable 8.2), its structure as well as its scope and its relation to other tasks, activities.

Section 3 – Clustering activities: Presents the main project’s clustering events, including meetings, technical conferences, interaction with the RIMS and EURMKB and interaction with the IAB.

Section 4 - Conclusions: Pertains to the conclusions of Deliverable 8.3.

3 Clustering activities

During the current period (first 24 months) the WP8's team has carried out the following transversal activities:

- Monthly meetings with WPs 7 and 9: Review of the progress of these WPs and discussion over challenges and next steps.
- Deliverable D8.1: Clustering Plan. This document aims to design the strategy, plan and activities to be implemented under the DigiEcoQuarry project, with a view to build progressively a collaborative network, consolidating the presence of the consortium partners in clusters and other relevant platforms.
- Deliverable D8.2: Protocols to cooperate with RMSI and EURMKD. This document aimed to design the strategy, plan and activities to be implemented under the DigiEcoQuarry project to provide and share information with these European Databases.
- Milestone MS8.1. International Advisory Board 1st meeting.
- The specific activities per task are described in the following subsections.

3.1 Clustering events

As mentioned in D8.1 "Clustering Plan", diverse types of clustering events are to be organized during the project:

- Technical & scientific workshops, conferences, events and trade fairs.
- Meetings with other projects and organizations.
- Clustering events with the Raw Materials Information System.

3.1.1 Organization and assistance to technical & scientific workshops, conferences, events and trade fairs

During the first 24 months of the project, we have participated in technical & scientific workshops, conferences, events and trade fairs:

- The first workshop of the European DigiEcoQuarry project took place on May 26th, 2022, during the VI Spanish National Aggregates Congress held in Oviedo. The session consisted of 8 presentations in which the general aspects of the project were presented, as well as some of the advanced techniques, machinery, and concepts on which it is based (Fig. 2). The program was as follows:
 - Drill to mill concept implementation by Pablo Segarra Catasús, Associate Professor at ETSI Minas y Energía of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid.
 - Digitalisation in surface drilling equipment by Enrique Mota López, General Manager at Sandvik Ibérica Mining and Rock Technology.
 - Automation of an aggregates' treatment plant by Sergio Alonso Aznar, director at ARCO MET 7 and ARCO ELECTRÓNICA.
 - DigiEcoQuarry: the future of the aggregates sector is already the present, by Lorena Viladés Santos, ANEFA's project department and DigiEcoQuarry's coordination team.
 - Digitalisation in the aggregates industry – Implementation, uses and success stories by Paulo Romero Martínez, ANEFA's project department and DigiEcoQuarry's coordination team.

- DigiEcoQuarry as a tool for monitoring the activities of the mobile fleet in mining by Diego Ignacio Laza Martín, Mining Project Manager of about.
- Vision of DigiEcoQuarry's pilots by Paolo Zambianchi, Manager at Holcim Italy.
- Digitalisation and cooperation in the DigiEcoQuarry Project by José Eugenio Ortiz Menéndez, Chair Professor at ETSI Minas y Energía of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid.

This series of lectures attracted a large group of attendees who are also committed to the digitalisation of the sector and perceive DigiEcoQuarry as a pioneering system in the mining sector. The video of the workshop can be accessed in the following site: <https://youtu.be/UV714oFZgF4> and [DEQ Zenodo community](#).

Figure 2 DigiEcoQuarry workshop during VI Spanish National Aggregates Congress.

- The DigiEcoQuarry Project joined the exciting qualifications for the Spanish Geology Olympics (Figure 3). Students and teachers took part in the different competitions held at Madrid’s School of Mines and Energy on the 3rd of March 2022. Important information and issues related to aggregates and quarries could not be missed in such an important event. In addition, topics about digitalization were widely discussed and practical examples were made to develop 3D models of minerals and rocks. A link of this event was posted in our webpage: <https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/03/10/welcome-to-the-spanish-geology-olympics/>.

Figure 3 Event organized by DigiEcoQuarry during the 2022 Spanish Geology Olympics.

- The DigiEcoQuarry Project took part in an educational event with a heterogenous public during the Expo Minerals exhibition held at Madrid’s School of Mines and Energy on March 13th, 2022 (Figure 4). During this event, we presented some of the main characteristics of aggregates and quarries. In addition, we brought up several topics about digitalization, explaining the processes involved in it and presenting some practical examples involving the development of 3D models of minerals and rocks. A link of this event was posted in our webpage: <https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/04/06/digiecoquarry-at-expominerals/>.

Figure 4 Event organized by DigiEcoQuarry during the 2022 the Expo Minerals exhibition.

- The DigiEcoQuarry Project organised field trips (April 9-11th, 2022 and April 21st, 2022) with university students to aggregate quarries in which the main objectives of this project were presented (Figure 5). In one of these visits, some students recorded a video explaining the main operations in aggregate quarries (Figure 6). A link to these events was posted on our social media: twitter, Instagram.

Figure 5 Field trip organized by DigiEcoQuarry Project to a recycled aggregate quarry.

Figure 6 Field trip organized by DigiEcoQuarry Project to a limestone quarry.

- The DigiEcoQuarry Project took part in the Raw Materials for the Green Transition Event, organised by the European Raw Materials Alliance and EIT Raw Materials. Policy makers, public and private organisations, companies and other stakeholders joined this event in which we made some contacts.

- XIII Iberian Geochemical Congress. 25-27 April 2022. We presented the communication: Geochemical characterisation of lacustrine formations of Central Spain (Ortiz, J.E., Torres, T., Sánchez-Palencia, Y., Quílez, L., Llamas, J., García, M.J., López Cilla, I.).
- The project organised an event with secondary school students (Figure 7). We presented some of the main characteristics of aggregates and quarries, including the main goals of DigiEcoQuarry project.
- We attended the Conference about Mining and Energy: future strategies (June 23rd, 2022) in which we contacted representatives of companies, organisations, policy makers and researchers.
- We presented an oral communication in the USATIC 2022 International Congress, named: La digitalización de minerales y rocas para la enseñanza virtual de Geología (Ortiz, J.E., Pérez, P., Herrero, M.J., López Cilla, I., Peña, C., Rodríguez-Rama, J.A., Escavy, J.I.).
- DigiEcoQuarry organised a Symposium named “Digitalization and TICs for teaching and research in Earth Sciences and Mining” within the International Congress on Evaluation of the Quality of Research and Higher Education (FECIES) (28-30 September 2022). In this Symposium we presented some advances about digitalisation to obtain 3D models and innovative ways to spread the knowledge about mining and geology. We also presented 2 oral communications:
 - Virtual teaching of Geology and Mining through MOOCs (Ortiz, J.E., López Cilla, I., Viladés, L., Luaces, C., Romero, P., Herrero, M.J., Escavy, J.I., Blanco, J.L., Martiarena, L., Eguillor, L., Rico, J., Gavilanes, J., Pérez, C., Sánchez-Palencia, Y.).
 - 3D Geological models and digitalization of outcrops (Herrero., Escavy, J.I., Pérez-Fortes, A.P., Ortiz, J.E., et al.).

Figure 7 Event with secondary school students.

- We presented an oral communication in the XII Iberian Congress of Acoustics (November 4th, 2022). This communication was awarded due to the quality of the results: Acercando los autocodificadores variacionales al gran público (Cámara Largo, M.J., Blanco Murillo, J.L.).
- The characteristics and goals of DigiEcoQuarry were presented in the Swedish Mining Innovation PhD Student network workshop (November 10-11th, 2022).
- We attended a Conference on Independence and Energy Geopolitics (November 16th, 2022).
- DigiEcoQuarry organised two events within the XXII Week of Science and Innovation (November 14th-16th, 2022) with the attendance of a heterogeneous public (Fig. 8). We presented the main characteristics of aggregates and quarries, and we showed a practical example of how we can easily digitalise and develop 3D models of minerals and rocks.

Figure 8 Events organized by DigiEcoQuarry during the XXII Week of Science and Innovation (November 2022).

- DigiEcoQuarry took part in the Raw Materials Week (November 14-18th, 2022), specifically the 9th Annual High-Level Conference of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) on raw materials.
- We attended a Conference on Energy sustainability & storage (December 15th, 2022).
- The Project organised an event with university students in which we presented the main goals of DigiEcoQuarry project (December 16th, 2022).
- We finished a Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) about aggregates named: “Aggregates: mining, uses, digitalization and sustainability. In this regard, we obtained additional funding to develop this course (Figure 9). The first edition began on May 16th, 2023 and there will be another edition in Autumn 2023, as well as two more per year, at least during 2024 and 2025. It is hosted on the MiriadaX online platform on the following link: <https://miriadax.net/curso/los-aridos-mineria-aplicacion-digitalizacion-y-sostenibilidad/>

This course is aimed at learning about the origin and processes of extraction, treatment and processing of aggregates, which are the most used raw materials after water, as well as learning about their application in daily life and in industry, including aspects related to sustainability, environment and social dimension, together with digitization and artificial intelligence of processes. It lasts for 80 hours (8 weeks) and contains 9 modules with the following structure:

- Module 1: Origin and types.
- Module 2: The aggregates sector.
- Module 3: Aggregate extraction.
- Module 4: Aggregate processing.
- Module 5: Types of aggregates.
- Module 6: Quality of aggregates and security.
- Module 7: Digitalization.
- Module 8: Environment.
- Module 9: Social dimension.

Figure 9 Making-of the MOOC on aggregates.

- We created an account in Research Gate (Figure 10) in order to share the scientific publications (<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Digiecoquarry-Project>). The goal of this organisation is to connect the world of science and make research open to all. It has 20 million researchers who come from diverse sectors in over 190 countries, and use ResearchGate to connect, collaborate, and share their work.

Figure 10 Detail of DigiEcoQuarry account in Research Gate.

- The DigiEcoQuarry Project organised a field trip (March 11-12th, 2023) with university students to aggregate quarries in which the main objectives of this project were presented (Figure 11).

Figure 11 Field trip organized by DigiEcoQuarry Project to a quarry in northern Spain.

- DigiEcoQuarry participated in the 1s Conference of the Digital Science and Innovation Platform on May 10th 2023. All the participants met together with companies and public administrations of interest, in the auditorium of the Center for Human and Social Sciences of Madrid. There were some round tables in which strategic issues such as cybersecurity, digitalisation, sustainability and technology were discussed.

In addition, we include the following a list of technical workshops related to aggregates and mining industry in which we shared and presented (oral communications & conferences) the goals and progress of DigiEcoQuarry:

- MIRO Forum (November 24-26th, 2021).
- Workshop with Swedish aggregate producers (**SBMI Production**) on process modelling and how to incorporate environmental impact in process evaluation (January 19th, 2022).
- South African Institute of Quarrying Conference (March 16-17th, 2022).
- Industry conference IMPC Asia-Pacific 2022 (Conference) (August 22nd, 2022).
- Sexto Encuentro Nacional de la Industria de Agregados-Colombia (September 7-9th, 2022).
- Sustainable Development in the Minerals Industry - SDIMI 2022 (Conference) (September 15th, 2022).
- Fragblast, Beijing (October 17-19th, 2022).
- Bauma 22 (October 24th, 2022).
- BIM Expo (November 15th, 2022).
- ANEPLA Ordinary assembly (November 25th, 2022).
- MIRO Forum (November 28th, 2022).
- Seminar for Advancement of the Aggregate Industry, Seoul (November 14-20th, 2022).
- AFA Extremadura and Castilla La Mancha meeting (February 14-15th, 2023).
- Workshop Holcim (March 8th, 2023). Holcim Italy organised a workshop in which the project and its developments were discussed.
- Prospectors & Developers Association of Canada-PDAC Convention (5th-8th, 2023). It is the World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention. Lorena Viladés, ANEFA's coordination team member, was part of the important delegation the European Commission sent to this Convention.
- Hannover Messe-EU Research & Innovation for Sustainable and Efficient Raw Materials Value Chains (April 17-21st, 2023). This event brings together leaders, innovators, and experts worldwide to showcase the latest developments and technologies and discuss the future of industrial manufacturing. Among the participants were: Robert Lindner (Policy Officer from the European Commission); Knobloch Andreas (Head of Competence Team Geology & Raw Materials at Beak Consultants GmbH); Ivo Zeller (Project manager at Steinbeis Europa Zentrum); Patrik Schumacher (Project Consultant at Steinbeis Europa Zentrum); Heimo Docter (Developer at Ericsson) and Tobias Mathiak (Senior Innovation Manager at K+S).
- Energy efficiency workshop (May 3rd, 2023). ANEFA organised a workshop about energy efficiency in aggregates sites with more than 40 attendees in which MAXAM and ANEFA and MAXAM explained their developments within the project.

- SaMoTer (May 3rd-7th, 2023), in Verona. It is the only event in Italy to embrace all sectors of construction machinery, and DEQ was present.
- ANEFA General Assembly (May 4th, 2023).

3.1.2 Meetings with other projects and organizations

One of the goals of DigiEcoQuarry is to establish links and synergies with international organizations and other interested stakeholders to provide wider dissemination. In this regard, synergies with other relevant EU-funded and national research projects and initiatives were pursued to facilitate knowledge interchange, gain mutual dissemination benefits and to exploit potential cooperation. We include the following a list of meetings with research **projects** and activities performed since the beginning of the project:

- Meeting with the International Network of Raw Materials Training Centres (INTERIM) Project (Horizon 2020).
- Meeting with Sustainable Management in the Extractive Industries (SUMEX) Project (Horizon 2020).
- Meeting with ROBOMINERS Project (Horizon 2020).
- Meeting with Next Generation Carbon Neutral Pilots for Smart Intelligent Mining Systems (NEXGEN – SIMS) (Horizon 2020).
- Meeting with the Project Raw Matters Ambassadors at Schools. December 2021 and 17/02/2022.
- Meetings and collaboration with the Project “Laboratorio Virtual de reconocimiento de minerales y rocas”.
- Meeting and collaboration with the Project “Realidad extendida: recorridos virtuales y modelos geológicos 3D para asignaturas de Grados de Ciencias de la Tierra”, funded by Universidad Complutense de Madrid. INNOVA-DOCENCIA.
- Meetings and collaboration with the Project “GAMEinLABEX: Gamificación en los laboratorios y ejercicios para la mejora de los resultados de aprendizaje”, funded by UPM.
- Meeting with the Project Better Geo Edu, funded by EIT Raw Materials.
- Meeting with Project DIG_IT, funded by the EU’s Horizon 2020.
- Meeting and collaboration with Project ROTATE, funded by the EU’s Horizon Europe.
- Meetings with Project IlluMINEation, funded by the EU’s Horizon 2020 (Figure 12). We plan to organise a future workshop with other projects, including SUMEX, ROBOMINERS, DIG_IT, ROTATE and IlluMINEation.

Figure 12 Meeting with leaders of IlluMINEation project.

- Of note, we have collaborated with some of these projects, namely: “Laboratorio Virtual de reconocimiento de minerales y rocas”, “Realidad extendida: recorridos virtuales y modelos geológicos 3D para asignaturas de Grados de Ciencias de la Tierra”, “GAMEinLABEX” and “ROTATE”. In some cases, we have obtained results which have been presented in Scientific Congresses.
- With the collaboration of some of these projects (“GAMEinLABEX: Gamificación en los laboratorios y ejercicios para la mejora de los resultados de aprendizaje”; “Laboratorio Virtual de reconocimiento de minerales y rocas”) we digitalized and created audiovisual material with descriptions of the main sedimentary, igneous and metamorphic rocks used as aggregates, which are posted in the webpage of our project (Figure 13): <https://digiecoquarry.eu/dissemination/>

Figure 13 Examples of some digitalized rocks used as aggregates posted in the webpage of the project.

- Meeting with Briefcase project, EIT Raw Materials. We will collaborate in some activities.
- Meeting with Project ICEBERG, funded by the EU's Horizon 2020. We will organise a technical workshop and collaborate.
- Meeting with RAWMINA, funded by the EU's Horizon 2020. We will organise activities together and share information.
- Meeting with IlluMINEation, ROBOMINERS, SUMEX, Sea4value, ROTATE, DIG_IT and MASTERMINE to explore synergies (Figure 14). We plan to collaborate in the future, have regular meetings, organise activities and workshops and share information.
- We have also contacted and had meetings with organizations having synergies with DigiEcoQuarry to share the objectives and results of our projects, such as ANEPLA, MIRO, PRIMIGEA, AINDEX, GAIN, COMINROC, CONFEDEM, EIT Raw Materials, EPIROC, FdeA, and UEPG, among others.
- DigiEcoQuarry members also had a meeting with the Directorate of industry, energy and mines of Andalusia (Spain), which is the governing body responsible for the resolution, management and execution powers attributed by the Spanish regulations in matters of mines. We presented our project and planned to collaborate in the future regarding the aggregates industry.

All these contacts are allowing WP8 and WP9 partners to monitor the efficiency of the dissemination and clustering activities.

Figure 14 Meeting with leaders of IlluMINEation, ROBOMINERS, SUMEX, Sea4value, ROTATE, DIG_IT and MASTERMINE projects (May 22nd, 2023).

3.1.3 Clustering events with RMIS

As mentioned before, one of the aims is to cooperate with other similar projects and initiatives. Individual meetings were held with other Raw Materials European projects, but DigiEcoQuarry also participated in clustering events consisting of general meetings coinciding with the annual Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) workshop. This workshop is organized in co-operation with the Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). The RMIS Workshop is aimed at professionals involved in designing and developing policies, projects and programmes around primary and secondary raw materials, in accordance with the Strategic Implementation Plan designed by the European Innovation Partnership on Raw Materials, chaired by the European Commission. This Workshop focuses on the links and knowledge exchanges between the RMIS and most relevant EU funded projects on raw materials. The aim is to provide an overview, improve the interactions between various H2020 projects and streamline the information flow and availability of these projects to the European Commission's RMIS. In this regard, these events are used to understand the synergies, gaps, overlaps and future research needs in relation to raw material (aggregates) projects.

- In this regard, DigiEcoQuarry Project participated in the 2021 JRC / HaDEA Technical Workshop "Channelling knowledge from European projects into the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)" which was held online on December 3rd (Figure 15). We were invited to participate and present the characteristics and objectives of our project. The aim of this workshop was to facilitate the efficient knowledge transfers from EU projects on raw materials (such as Horizon 2020/Europe, and EIT Raw Materials projects) into the RMIS, so that project's outputs can best contribute to the RMIS & EU policy objectives. At the workshop, 17 projects were presented, including DigiEcoQuarry, while more than 30 participated as technical audience. The opening session featured presentations from Constantin CIUPAGEA (HoU, Land Resources, JRC), Victoria PETROVA (HoU, Industry, HaDEA), Luca MARMO (Senior expert, SDGs, Green Finance & Economic Analysis, DG ENV), Patrick NADOLL (Senior Advisor, EIT Raw Materials), and Ioannis BAKAS (European Environment Agency - EEA). Links to this event were posted in the RMIS webpage: <https://www.era-min.eu/news/era-min-2021-jrc-hadea-technical-workshop-rmis>; <https://hadea.ec.europa.eu/events/workshop-channelling-knowledge-european-projects-raw-materials->

[information-system-rmis-2021-12-03_en](https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/01/21/digiecoquarry-project-participated-in-the-2021-jrc-hadea-technical-workshop/), and also in our webpage: <https://digiecoquarry.eu/2022/01/21/digiecoquarry-project-participated-in-the-2021-jrc-hadea-technical-workshop/>.

Figure 15 Participation of DigiEcoQuarry in the 2021 RMIS workshop (December 3rd, 2021).

- DigiEcoQuarry Project also participated in the 2022 JRC / HaDEA Technical Workshop “Channelling knowledge from European projects into the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)” which was held online on October 14th, 2022 (Fig. 16). At the workshop 10 projects were presented. The opening session featured presentations from Constantin CIUPAGEA (HoU, Land Resources, JRC), Victoria PETROVA (HoU, Industry, HaDEA), Ignacio CALLEJA (EIT Raw Materials), Peder JENSEN (European Environment Agency - EEA) and Philip NUSS (DE-UBA & ETC/EEA).

Figure 16 Invitation to participate in the RMIS workshop (October 14th 2022).

3.2 Cooperation with the Raw Materials Information System and European Raw Materials Knowledge Base

To disseminate international public information about DigiEcoQuarry Project, it was planned to provide data to the Raw Materials Information System and the European Raw Materials Knowledge Base.

The **Raw Materials Information System** (RMIS) aims to be a central European Union gateway of knowledge on primary and secondary raw materials. RMIS 2.0 was officially launched in November 2017, its structure supports the collection, organization, storage and communication of information on raw materials and, to a certain degree, on products derived from them.

RMIS 2.0 is organized in thematic sections, one of which being the “Raw Materials Knowledge Gateway” (RMKG). The RMKG constitutes a key part of the RMIS because it provides a unified access point to knowledge on raw materials from different providers at national, European and international levels. Through the RMKG, it is intended to engage a broad range of knowledge providers into the development of the RMIS. In turn, this gateway allows knowledge providers to promote and increase the visibility of their data, information and knowledge on raw materials, among various stakeholders. The RMIS 2.0 also facilitates knowledge coordination and harmonization, as well as other joint activities. In this way, it is aimed that DigiEcoQuarry will be able to contribute to consolidate and expand EU knowledge on raw materials.

The **European Union Raw Materials Knowledge Base** (EURMKB) is a part of the European Innovation Partnership’s Strategic Implementation Plan. Its aim is to be a one-stop-shop for all information on raw materials in the EU. With the help of EU countries, the service will collect, store, maintain, upgrade, analyse, and disseminate information on the raw materials. This knowledge base will serve industry and policy makers as a valuable source of data. By now we have contacted the EURMKB and the Joint Research Centre.

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) developed a detailed guideline for exchanging various types of project information for inclusion in the RMIS – Raw Materials Gateway (<http://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>).

In this regard, we provided information about DigiEcoQuarry to the Raw Materials Knowledge Gateway in July 2021, including a supporting link to our website (Annex I). In the RMIS we have a dedicated webpage space (Figure 17 and Figure 18) to show the type of raw materials’ related knowledge that our Project has available and that we want to include in the RMKG. We could freely structure that content and proposed the way of presenting it. We also included a visual identifier for the Project and a short description with different thematic sections. The future updates will then be coordinated together with the RMKG. Knowledge is divided into “National level”, and “European level”. The RMIS team is interacting closely with us.

Figure 17 RMIS webpage with the EU funded projects marked in red.

Figure 18 Webspace of DigiEcoQuarry in the RMIS webpage (in cooperation with HaDEA and EIR Raw Materials) in which selected EU funded raw materials Projects are shown.

As mentioned in Section 3.1.3 DigiEcoQuarry Project participated in the 2021 and 2022 JRC / HaDEA Technical Workshop “Channelling knowledge from European projects into the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)”.

3.3 Cooperation with the International Advisory Board (IAB)

Diverse organizations of Europe including companies, press media and policy makers related to the aggregates and quarrying sector are included in the IAB (Table 1) in order to provide valuable external input, advice and feedback, especially when the project may experience difficulties. Nevertheless, members of the IAB will be contacted as necessary during the execution of the Project. The aim is also to attract as many key stakeholders as necessary to maximize the impact of the Project.

Table 1. Members of the International Advisory Board of DigiEcoQuarry Project.

MEMBER	COUNTRY	CHARACTERISTICS
EU – OSHA – European Agency for Safety & Health (From European Union)	EU (Bilbao /Brussels)	H&S policy maker
Global Aggregates Information Network– GAIN	World (Ireland)	Aggregates organization
International Union for Conservation of Nature's -IUCN	World (Switzerland)	Environmental NGO
Aggregates Business Europe	United Kingdom	Press media
UEPG –European Aggregates Association	EU (Brussels)	Aggregates Association
European Geological Surveys	EU (Brussels)	European Association of Geological Surveys
Federal Association of Mineral Raw Materials E.V. (BV MIRO)	Germany	Aggregates organization
Hanson Hispania – Heidelberg Cement Group	World (Spain)	Aggregates company

The IAB will provide input, advice and feedback for:

- System validation, replicability and up-scaling: as an entity made up of aggregates companies, explosive and machinery, manufacturers and potential end users, their feedback during the validation phase of the project will prove to be fundamental in the refining of the final solution and the definition of key quality standards.
- Transition to market: the IAB will aid in the easing of the transition of the DigiEcoQuarry solution from a prototype to a commercial product by building up a realistic customer base and identifying target markets.
- Broadening the project’s reach: working directly with relevant agents in the sector will contribute to widening the project’s horizons regarding international relevance and overall impact, since the IAB will be kept informed of any new developments and events and will be encouraged to take part in the project’s execution.

All partners of the IAB were contacted during July-August 2021 and we organised the 1st Meeting of the International Advisory Board (Milestone 8.1) on November 16th, 2021. The agenda of the Meeting is shown in Table 2.

After the introduction of the project by the Project Coordinator (PC), César Luaces, ANEFA, all the assistants were presented:

- Lothar LIKE, European Agency.
- Jim O’Brien, H&S social aspects. 2008 president of UEPG.
- Guy Woodford, Editor of Aggregates Business Europe & Aggregates Business International magazines.

- Dirk Fincke, Secretary General at UEPG.
- Walter Nelles, Vicechair in UEPG and MIRO
- César Fernández, Performance Manager from HANSON.
- Daniel Oliveira. EuroGEOsurveys.
- José Eugenio Ortiz, UPM Madrid School of Mines, DEQ's WP8 Leader.
- Leire Martiarena, ZABALA Innovation Team, DEQ's WP7 Leader.
- Violeta Vázquez, ZABALA Management Team, DEQ's WP10 Participant.
- Lorena Viladés, ANEFA Coordination Team, DEQ's WP9 Leader.
- Paulo Romero, ANEFA Coordination Team, DEQ's WP1 Leader.

Table 2 Agenda of the 1st Meeting of the IAB (November 16th, 2021).

Agenda Item	Description of the agenda item	Time
Part 1		
Introduction	Welcome by the Coordinator and Introduction to the agenda [ANEFA] – César Luaces The role of the International Advisory Board Quick 'roundtable' (name, organisation, position)	10h30 to 10h45
Project Review	Review of the project rationale, structure, objectives & challenges - Presentation of the Project Programme Health & Safety / Environment / Social / Site economic & technical management [ANEFA] – César Luaces	10h45 to 11h00
Part 2		
Social	Social dimension [ZABALA] – Leire Martiarena	11h42 to 11h00
Clustering	Clustering strategy [UPM-AI] – José Eugenio Ortiz	12h00to 12h20
Dissemination	Dissemination strategy [ANEFA] – Lorena Viladés	12h20 to 12h35
Part 3		
Follow up	Proposed follow up plan [UPM-AI] – José Eugenio Ortiz	12h35 to 12h45
Conclusions	Conclusions of the 1st IAB meeting [ANEFA] – César Luaces Debate & approval	12h45 to 13h00
End of the meeting		13h00

The meeting ended with a proposed follow up plan, which included the minutes of the 1st IAB meeting, a non-disclosure agreement, implementation of IAB suggestions, evaluation of DEQ activities yearly by the IAB meetings, and D8.3 and D8.4 report on interactions with other organizations, projects and IAB. In addition, the IAB was asked to help DEQ to establish contact with other companies/projects. We also included a proposal of connections to be made (Table 3).

Table 3 Proposal of connections to be made by the IAB.

Member of IAB	Connection with other projects	Connection with Policy makers	Scalability Exploitation	Communication	Other areas of interest
EU – OSHA – European Agency for Safety & Health (From European Union)	X	X			Advise on H&S issues Some statistics Digitalisation risk approach Link with some campaigns
Global Aggregates Information Network – GAIN	X		X	X	Advise on social approach
International Union for Conservation of Nature's - IUCN	X				Advise on environmental issues Advise on social approach
Aggregates Business Europe	X		X	X	Advise on communication issues Advise on social approach
UEPG – European Aggregates Association	X	X	X	X	Advise on social approach
European Geological Surveys	X	X			Advise on geology and access to resources issues
Federal Association of Mineral Raw Materials E.V. (BV MIRO)	X	X	X		Advise on social approach
Hanson Hispania – HeidelbergCement Group			X	X	Advise on aggregates industry

Although it was planned to have two meetings with the IAB, one at the beginning and one at the end of the Project, we had another meeting on March 6th, 2023 with the Agenda shown in Table 4. The Meeting began with a summary by the Project Coordinator (PC), César Luaces, ANEFA, of what was done in the project. He also commented on the indications made by the PO, Marko Cacanowski, and Yannik Descantes. In addition, the WP 7, 8 and 9 leaders prepared 4 surveys related to 1-clustering activities, 2-communication with policy makers and public bodies, 3-social dimension and 4-dissemination and communication, that were prepared and shared among the members of the IAB to collect their feedback about different topics of the project (Annex II).

Table 4 Agenda of the 2nd Meeting with the IAB (March 6th, 2023).

Agenda Item	Description of the agenda item	Time
Part 1-Introduction		
Introduction	Welcome by the Coordinator and Introduction to the agenda [ANEFA] – César Luaces Current project status [ANEFA] – César Luaces	9h00 to 9h20
Project Review	Roundtable and questions	9h20 to 9h35
Part 2-Discussion		
Clustering	Proposals for the improvement of clustering activities with other entities and projects. [UPM-AI] – José Eugenio Ortiz	9h35 to 9h55
Policy makers	Proposals for the interaction with policymakers. [ANEFA] – César Luaces	9h55 to 10h15
Social	How to increase social acceptance in the extractive industry [ZABALA] – Leire Martiarena	10h15to 10h35
Dissemination	Proposals for broadening the impact of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities. [ANEFA] – Lorena Viladés	10h35 to 10h55
Part 3-End		
	Next steps	10h55 to 11h00
	Any other business	
	Date of next meeting	

The results of the 4 surveys are shown in Table 5 and, Figure 19, Figure 20 and Figure 21. Based on the comments and feedback provided by the members of the IAB, in the future we will focus on some actions.

1.-Please rate which of these activities you believe to be more effective for clustering:

2.-Please rate from 0 to 10 how do you think that we can increase our interaction with other projects

3.-Which activities for the general public you believe to be more effective for clustering:

Figure 19 Results of survey related to clustering activities shared by the members of the IAB.

Table 5 Results of survey related to communication with policy makers and public bodies shared by the members of the IAB. A total of 10 members filled out the survey. They rate from 1 (not relevant at all) to 10 (extremely relevant) how important they believe were the objectives of communication with policy makers.

Question	Average
1. To contribute to the development and improvement of legislation.	9.2
2. To contribute to new Raw Materials policies, projects and roadmaps.	8.5
3. To align new, innovative quarrying and mining systems with public policies.	8.2
4. To get in touch with other national and EU initiatives, projects, platforms and networks.	8.0
5. To cooperate on an international scale.	8.3
6. To remove regulatory restrictions or obstacles related to Environment.	7.7
7. To remove regulatory restrictions or obstacles related to Health & Safety.	7.1
8. To contribute to standardisation processes.	7.7
9. To contribute to regulatory compliance.	8.1
10. To raise awareness about the aggregates sector.	8.5
11. To mediate between scale experimentation and policymaking.	7.2
12. To use EU dissemination channels.	7.2
<i>Response: "To raise the visibility and innovative approach of the industry."</i>	
14. Parliament and other legislative and representative bodies. – EU.	8.6
15. Parliament and other legislative and representative bodies. – National.	8.7
16. Parliament and other legislative and representative bodies. – Regional and Local.	8.4
17. Public Administrations and governments – EU.	8.2
18. Public Administrations and governments. – National.	8.6
19. Public Administrations and governments. – Regional and Local.	8.7
20. Research and academic stakeholders.	7.2
21. Technological centres	7.6
22. Standardisation bodies.	7.3
23. Entrepreneurs organisations.	7.3
24. Corporate aggregates companies.	8.5
25. Technology suppliers.	8.5
26. Construction industry associations.	7.4
27. Trade Unions.	7.5
28. Environmental NGOs.	7.9
29. Environmental networks.	7.1
30. Thinktanks.	6.6
31. International governance organisations.	6.9

Question	Average
32. Other lobbyist entities.	5.0
33. Other key general public stakeholders.	5.8
34. Media and journalists.	8.0
35. Could you suggest any additional group of policymakers?	"GAIN"
36. The conceptual aspects of the project.	8.3
37. The technical achievements of the project.	8.7
38. The scientific knowledge the project created.	8.3
39. The full range of project activities.	7.9
40. Could you suggest any additional topic?	¿?
41. Legal Background and Further Regulation.	7.5
42. General Ethical Principles in the DEQ Grant Agreement.	8.6
43. Compliance with EU Transparency Register.	8.5
44. Complementary ethical principles to be applied.	7.4
45. Could you suggest any additional principle?	-
46. To remove obstacles and red tape that slow down investments.	9.1
47. To implement a 'one in, one out' approach to minimise regulatory burden for citizens and businesses.	7.7
48. To mainstream the Sustainable Development Goals of the UN.	8.5
49. Could you suggest any additional requirement?	-
50. Green Deal and 2030 climate framework.	8.6
51. EU principles for sustainable raw materials.	8.2
52. UN Sustainable Development Goals.	8.6
53. EU digital policies.	8.5
54. H&S regulations.	8.5
55. Could you suggest any additional political and regulatory framework?	"Renewable Energy Directive"
56. In your opinion, what strategy would be the most effective to improve communication with policymakers? (please clarify).	"Site visits"
57. Periodic and recurrent communication delivery. (Dissemination of project materials).	8.3
58. Specific communication according to needs. (Case by case communication).	8.6
59. Direct interaction. (Meetings and policy briefings).	9.3
60. Direct interaction. (Enquiries & surveys).	7.2
61. Direct interaction. (Workshops/seminars/conferences).	9.0
62. Could you suggest any additional option?	-

Question	Average
63. In your opinion, how may we encourage aggregates' industry companies to use the project's products, developments and technologies?	Plot
<p>64. In your opinion, what are the project's strengths in relation to the industry? (please limit the number to three):</p> <p>Responses: "The effective implementation of sustainability criteria and efficiency of mining operations."</p> <p>"Innovation and possibility to save energy"</p>	
<p>65. In your opinion, what are the project's weaknesses in relation to the industry? (please limit the number to three).</p> <p>Responses: "The inertia of the mining industry in adapting processes to new paradigms."</p> <p>"Upfront investment for companies"</p>	
66. On a scale from 1 (not aligned at all) to 10 (extremely aligned), please, rate how much the project's objectives are aligned with the extractive industry's ones.	8.9
67. In your opinion, may the industry employees reject using new technologies such as digitisation and AI? Please, rate from 1 (no rejection) to 10 (rejection).	6.5
68. In your opinion, may the use of new technologies, such as digitisation and AI, cause new risks for the mining industry workers? Please, rate from 1 (no new risks) to 10 (relevant new risks).	5.0
<p>69. Now that you know more about the project, how can we achieve international dissemination? (Please specify).</p> <p>Responses: "Through the presentation in fairs and international congresses of the achievements, even partial, obtained in the pilot sites."</p> <p>"GAIN, UNEP"</p>	
<p>70. Now that you know more about the project, do you have any further proposals for our exploitation business plan? (Please specify).</p> <p>Responses: "Not really at this stage."</p> <p>"Meeting with EU decision makers"</p>	

1.-How relevant is social acceptance for extractive industries?

2.-Please briefly explain why you selected the previous option. We want to better understand your perspective and opinions.

Currently, all administrative processes related to the authorization of mining industries are the subject of public information and consultations with "You have to take the local community with you. As much open dialogue, quarry site visits, visits to local schools as possible. The importance of quarrr" "Without social acceptance there is no operation feasible "

3.-Which is the current level of social acceptance? In general, would you say the extractive industry is more accepted?

4.-Please briefly explain why you selected the previous option. We want to better understand your perspective and opinions.

"The bad social perception of the mining industry, derived from past times. This perception has been transferred to the new generations. It is very nec" "Some people understand the need to extract mineral products to sustain and enhance quality of life. Many do not fully see the link. They only see dirt" "Not in my back yard principle "

5.-What are the main barriers to gaining social acceptance?

6.Any other barrier that are relevant, and why?

7.-What kind of actions can be taken to address the barriers you have identified? Which are the most effective? (Select the four you consider most effective)

8.-Would you like to highlight any good practices to communicate and interact with local authorities and communities?
"1)Some type of local incentive: sports sponsorship, community gardens, cultural events, etc. that bring the industry closer to its immediate social en"

9.-What is your opinion on the concept of social license to operate? Is it a useful tool?

10.- In your experience, what are some of the key factors that contribute to employee acceptance of digitalization and procedure changes?

11.-What are the biggest barriers to gain the employees acceptance of digitalization and procedure changes?

12.-How can organizations improve their efforts to engage with and support their workers?

13.- Do you know any good practice in the sector to upskill and reskill employees, particularly as new technologies and practices continue to emerge?
"1) Continuous training 2) Incentives on positive results. (Nothing new)"

Figure 20 Results of survey related to social dimension shared by the members of the IAB.

1.-Could you please write the official webpage(s) of your organisation?
<https://www.asturias.es>; <https://www.dstsgps.com/intro-pt-pt/#/intro>; www.GAIN.le

2. Does your organisation use any of these social media?

3. Does your organisation post just about it or does it also share information about related initiatives?

4. Does your organisation have a newsletter?

5. If yes, would it be possible to send you articles about the project and publish them?

6. Does your company hold any events in which we could present our project?

7. Please indicate the name of the event.
"NZ meeting"

8. We would like to establish a solid communication with your organisation. If you think you might have any idea or field in which we could collaborate and work together, please let us know.
This is a public administration, subject to the specific legal regime of the public sector; All collaboration with third parties is established through: "Brief project updates"

Figure 21 Results of the survey related to dissemination and communication shared by the members of the IAB.

The activities carried out within WP8 have provided valuable material for dissemination, which has been posted in the social media of DigiEcoQuarry project (webpage, facebook, twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn) (Figure 22).

Figure 22 Examples of some activities of WP8 posted in the social media of the project.

4 Conclusions

As stated in the Grant Agreement, at the middle of the DigiEcoQuarry project (2023) WP8 has developed “Deliverable 8.3: Report on interactions with other organizations, projects and the IAB (1|2)” which contains the results of the clustering plan carried out involving Tasks T8.1, T8.2 and T8.3.

In this regard, we have identified and developed clustering possibilities as stated in Deliverables D8.1 and D8.2 of DigiEcoQuarry Project, which in these 24 months were:

- Contacts and meetings with projects, initiatives and organizations to explore synergies with DigiEcoQuarry project.
- Co-operation with some of these projects. In this regard, we have produced material which has been presented in Scientific Congress or hosted on our web page.
- Organization and assistance to technical workshops/conferences. We have contacted policy makers, representatives of companies, organisations, researchers and leaders of other projects.
- Meeting with the Directorate of industry, energy and mines of Andalusia (Spain). We plan to collaborate in the future regarding the aggregates industry.
- Organization of activities and events with students and general public: conferences, practical demonstrations, field trips, etc.
- Presentation of oral communications in scientific and educational congresses.
- Account in Research Gate to share the scientific publications of DigiEcoQuarry.
- Account in Zenodo as general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program.
- Development of a massive online open course (MOOC) about aggregates: mining, uses, digitalization and sustainability. We obtained co-funding for this purpose.
- Attendance to clustering events and workshops of the RMIS and the Raw Materials Week.
- Cooperation with the Raw Materials Information System and European Raw Materials Knowledge Base.
- Cooperation with the IAB. We organized two meetings to obtain feedback.

In brief, the outcomes of the clustering activities are providing input not only to all DigiEcoQuarry’s WPs, but also to other stakeholders. The outcomes are being disseminated via the planned activities and channels described in D8.1 and in the communication plan (WP9). In this regard, we will continue working on the Clustering plan. We also are taking into account the feedback provided by the IAB.

At the end of the DigiEcoQuarry project (May 2025) WP8 will produce “Deliverable 8.4: Report on interactions with other organizations, projects and the IAB (2|2)”. This final Deliverable will compile the results of the clustering plan carried out during the full length of the Project and a summary of the clustering events and activities organized.

5 References

- DIGIECOQUARRY Project Description of Action Annex A.
- DIGIECOQUARRY Project Description of Action Annex B.
- Deliverable 8.1 “Clustering Plan of the DIGIECOQUARRY project”.
- Deliverable 8.2 “Protocols to cooperate with RMIS and EURMKB”.

6 Annex I. Information provided to the RMKG for the dedicated webpage space in the RMIS

Overview

DIGIECOQUARRY is a H2020 Project addressing the topic C5-10-2019-2020, which will exploit the aggregates industry's great potential through a coordinated approach towards construction materials management with the final goal of reducing EU external supply dependency as well as leading an efficient use of resources. The project will develop systems, technology and processes for integrated digitisation and automation real-time process control, to be piloted in 5 EU quarries. The development of innovative an Intelligent Quarrying System will increase the sustainable supply of minerals for the construction sector as well as enabling the sustainable extraction of EU's mineral resources in existing and new quarries.

Activities on raw materials

DIGIECOQUARRY aims to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an **Innovative Quarrying System (IQS)** comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide **integrated digitalised, automatic and real-time process control for aggregates quarries**. This will translate into:

- 1. Improved Health, Safety and Security conditions for workers**, avoiding their exposure to dangerous operations through automated and controlled processes.
- 2. Improved Selectivity and Efficiency of the aggregates extractive sites**, thus increasing the **profitability** of the quarrying processes, ensuring long-term operational sustainability.
- 3. Maximised Sustainability and Resource Efficiency in the quarry operations** by reducing emissions, improving the management of water and fostering a sustainable supply of raw materials to feed new and existing value chains closing minerals loops and ensuring a long-lasting production.
- 4. Improved social acceptance** through the communication with policy makers, citizens and relevant actors to get them involved in the value chain. DIGIECOQUARRY will seek for international cooperation within the EU but also beyond, to share knowledge and best practices and improve the general perception of the quarrying industry.

The novel technologies will be piloted in 5 EU quarries with different characteristics to demonstrate ensure representative and transferable results, with a market-oriented approach.

Raw materials of interest

The cases investigated comprise a range of aggregates, including primary extraction of different types of materials (limestones, sands and gravels, andesites,...), and recycling processes in treatment plants.

Statutory, IPR issues

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 program, delivered by the European Health and Digital Executive Agency addressing the topic "Raw materials innovation actions: exploration and Earth observations in support of sustainable mining (C5-10-2019-2020)".

Most results and documents will be public, while few will be confidential (only available for members of the consortium, including the Commission Services).

Public data and documents will be hosted in the web page of the project (<http://digiecoquarry.eu/>). Use of the data constitutes citation to the original source

The following IPR components have been identified:

- Data from participants: Collected data will be treated with the highest confidentiality. Procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction will comply with national and the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).

- Technical reports for project monitoring and reporting: Technical reports shall be elaborated considering a fluent workflow. Therefore, the Project Management Handbook will include the procedures required to guarantee that project documents are produced, updated, distributed and stored correctly and efficiently

- Data from the pilots: This information will reflect the impacts that the proposed concepts/solutions have had under real operation. Key results will be disseminated among all the involved stakeholders. A particular effort will be made towards policy makers to highlight the benefits of adopting such strategies. All the results generated during the course of the project will be subject to the decision of the Partners with the supervision of the PC and the EB if they will be disseminated/shared or exploited/protected.

- Scientific Publications in International Journals, Scientific Conferences, EU Events, Trade Fairs and Workshops: Results on scientific achievements in field test site validations will be disseminated among the scientific community, industry, and further stakeholders in specific events. The publications shall include acknowledgements to the project and shall be communicated to the technical coordination.

- Partners will have to provide open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications, relating to its results scientific, that can be read online according to H2020 Guidelines on OA to Scientific Publications. Peer-reviewed publications will be stored in an open access repository (i.e. green open access), during and after the project.

Economics and trade

This project will demonstrate a market potential and the competitive technology advantage that will be gained through the pilot leading to expanding the EU business and to be implemented across the EU after the project is finished. DIGIECOQUARRY will revolutionise the aggregates industry with a set of products and services with proven market potential to be up-taken across the EU and beyond, as detailed in the Exploitation strategy. Specifically, with clear economic impacts, including a rise of total incomes, cost reduction, more investment in research and development, reduce of consumables, etc.

The exploitation methodology created in the project is fully aligned with the structure suggested in the Raw Materials Work Programme. DIGIECOQUARRY already satisfies all exploitation requirements listed below:

- Improved product robustness and reliability.
- Matching European value chains.
- Standardisation.
- IPR and technology transfer.
- Sustainability of financing.
- Improving the social acceptance of the quarrying industry.

It is planned to provide patent/utility models applications and new/enhanced products and services as DIGIECOQUARRY portfolio.

Secondary raw materials & circular economy

The EU Green Deal presents a roadmap with several actions aiming to boost the efficient use of resources by moving to a clean and circular economy; and restoring biodiversity and cut pollution. DIGIECOQUARRY will run within 6/9 EU Green Deal's policy areas: [1] Biodiversity, protecting existing fragile ecosystems and creating new biodiversity rich habitats; [2] Sustainable industry, ensuring more sustainable and environmentally friendly production cycles including circular economy; [3] Building and renovating, supplying huge amounts of local aggregates needed for renovation and improving the energy performance, [4] Sustainable mobility and [5] Climate action by climate change prevention and adaptation; and [6] Eliminating pollution, reducing impacts to enhance air quality, clean water, and prevent soil contamination from the quarry installations/equipment.

Aiming to meet the 2030 climate goals this project envisages a significant cut in the greenhouse gas emissions and improvement of energy efficiency in the production process. The following achievements are expected in the long term: [1] Expected achievements by 2030: a quarry operation based on the DIGIECOQUARRY concept will have its deposit digitalised (converted by AI planning procedures into operational activities) based on the principles of responsible production. The whole machinery of a production site will operate autonomously and run on efficient, environmental and safety-based principles. Production control and material flow management will be based on maximising the RM use. These step change technologies are designed to work in both big and SME-fit operations, helping the huge amount of small to medium

sized operations to work under sustainable principles; [2] Expected achievements by 2050: the next improvement step will involve operational site control by satellite technologies (Copernicus), realising operations on the principles of zero-impact in terms of water, wastes and carbon emissions, lowering energy consumption. Thus, every Quarry operation will contribute to increase biodiversity and create new attractive living areas of enriched status, both for people, animals and plants.

Monitoring raw materials sectors

One of the aims is to lead improved efficiency of processes maximizing quarry resources and sustainable management of water, energy emissions, minimised environmental impact and expanding the EU aggregates and construction business. Coupling Artificial Intelligence approaches with cyber-physical systems and the Internet of Things concept, make Industry 4.0 approach possible and the smart sustainable extractive site a reality. All phases of the process, from extraction to the end user are covered by DIGIECOQUARRY, ensuring communication with policy makers, social acceptance activities and international cooperation to share knowledge and best practices. The development of innovative an Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) will increase the sustainable supply of minerals for the construction sector as well as enabling the sustainable extraction of EU's mineral resources in existing and new quarries.

Artificial Intelligence will be used to close the circle around the optimisation of a digital quarry, it allows the information to be an asset in economic, environmental or human terms since it will automatically evolve and improve over time. Artificial Intelligence will be divided into six essential phases comprising: 1) Information analysis and filtering; 2) Design of the algorithm; 3) Algorithm training; 4) Industrial architecture design; 5) Testing of the algorithm; 6) Coordination and iteration.

Data accessibility

Data will be reported in the project deliveries and relevant extracts will be linked to the project website (<http://digiecoquarry.eu/>) most of them will be public, while few of them confidential. Research will be published in scientific and professional journals, and presented in international congresses and technical conferences.

The Project will also contribute to improve the awareness of relevant external stakeholders and the general public across the EU about the importance of Raw Materials for society, the challenges related to their supply within the EU and about proposed solutions which could help to improve society's acceptance of and trust in sustainable Raw Material production in the EU, duly taking into account the applicable EU environmental legislation.

DIGIECOQUARRY will ensure transfer of knowledge and cooperation among the relevant stakeholders, also feeding results from the pilots into the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) and European Raw Materials Knowledge Base (EURAMKB) databases. Workshops will be organized involving stakeholders, users, potential clients.

All data information security management will follow the guidelines of ISO (IEC 27002). The project will define specific business models and exploitation plans for the new products and services implemented in the project in order to ensure their future market uptake.

Research and Innovation

Results of this project are planned to be published in several scientific journals and presented in numerous scientific conferences. Moreover, partners will participate in diverse events (technical conferences/fairs) and 3 guidance roadmaps for the extractive industry will be developed.

Links and contacts

The partners of the Consortium are listed below:

Asociación Nacional de Empresarios Fabricantes de Áridos ([ANEFA](#))
GRANULATS VICAT ([VICAT](#))
HANSON HISPANIA SA ([HANSON](#))
Holcim Agregati Calcestruzzi SRL([HOLCIM](#))
CRONENBERGER STEININDUSTRIE FRANZ TRICHES GMBH & CO KG ([CSI](#))
AGREPOR AGREGADOS -EXTRACCAO DE INERTES, SA ([CIMPOR](#))
SANDVIK MINING AND CONSTRUCTION OY ([SANDVIK](#))
METSO OUTOTEC FINLAND OY ([Metso Minerals](#))
MAXAMCORP INTERNATIONAL SL ([Maxam corp](#))
ITK ENGINEERING GMBH ([ITK](#))
MONTANUNIVERSITAET LOEBEN ([MUL](#))
CHALMERS TEKNISKA HOEGSKOLA AB ([CHALMERS](#))
UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID ([UPM](#))
AKKA HIGH TECH ([AKKA](#))
ARCO ELECTRONICA SOCIEDAD ANONIMA ([ARCO](#))
MA ESTRO SRL ([Ma-estro SRL](#))
DOHMEN HERZOG & PARTNER GMBH ([DH&P](#)) /
ABAUT GMBH ([Aabout GmbH](#))
APP CONSULTORIA DE GESTION DE PROYECTOS S.L. ([APP Consultoria](#))
SIGMA TECHNOLOGIES SLU ([SIGMA](#))
CONSEJERIA DE INDUSTRIA, EMPLEO Y PROMOCION ECONOMICA ([DGASTUR](#))
ASOCIACION COLOMBIANA DE PRODUCTORES DE AGREGADOS PETREOS
([Asograsas](#))
MINTEK ([MINTEK](#))
ZABALA INNOVATION CONSULTING, S.A. ([ZABALA](#))
ROCTIM AB ([ROCTIM](#))

7

7 Annex II. Surveys shared among the members of the IAB related to 1-clustering activities, 2-communication with policy makers and public bodies, 3-social dimension and 4-dissemination and communication to collect their feedback about different topics of the project

International Advisory Board
Second Meeting
6th March 2023
Surveys

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2nd IAB meeting
March 2023

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2nd IAB meeting
March 2023

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1 Clustering activities survey

1) Please rate which of these activities you believe to be more effective for clustering:

- Organising seminars.
- Attending conferences.
- Presenting oral communications at scientific congresses.
- Attending technical fairs.
- Organising field trips to quarries.
- Sending newsletters.

2) Please rate how you believe we can increase our interaction with other projects:

- Holding meetings to share information.
- Organising workshops with other projects.
- Co-organising online seminars for students.

3) Which activities for the general public do you believe to be more effective?

- Conferences.
- Practical examples.
- Organising field trips to quarries.
- Organising competitions about aggregates/mining features for schools.

4) Can you suggest any other clustering activity?

2 Policymakers survey

1) On a scale from 0 (not relevant at all) to 10 (extremely relevant), please rate how important you believe the main objectives of communication with policymakers are:

- To contribute to the development and improvement of legislation.
- To contribute to new Raw Materials policies, projects and roadmaps.
- To align new, innovative quarrying and mining systems with public policies.
- To get in touch with other national and EU initiatives, projects, platforms and networks.
- To cooperate on an international scale.
- To remove regulatory restrictions or obstacles related to Environment.
- To remove regulatory restrictions or obstacles related to Health & Safety.
- To contribute to standardisation processes.
- To contribute to regulatory compliance.
- To raise awareness about the aggregates sector.
- To mediate between scale experimentation and policymaking.
- To use EU dissemination channels.

Could you suggest any additional objective?

2) On a scale from 0 (not relevant at all) to 10 (extremely relevant), please rate the following groups of policymakers involved in the extractive industry:

- Parliament and other legislative and representative bodies. – EU.
- Parliament and other legislative and representative bodies. – National.
- Parliament and other legislative and representative bodies. – Regional and Local.
- Public Administrations and governments – EU.
- Public Administrations and governments. – National.
- Public Administrations and governments. – Regional and Local.
- Research and academic stakeholders.
- Technological centres
- Standardisation bodies.
- Entrepreneurs organisations.
- Corporate aggregates companies.
- Technology suppliers.
- Construction industry associations.
- Trade Unions.
- Environmental NGOs.

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- Environmental networks.
- Thinktanks.
- International governance organisations.
- Other lobbyist entities.
- Other key general public stakeholders.
- Media and journalists.

Could you suggest any additional group of policymakers?

3) On a scale from 0 (not relevant at all) to 10 (extremely relevant), please rate the following main topics to disclose to policymakers:

- The conceptual aspects of the project.
- The technical achievements of the project.
- The scientific knowledge the project created.
- The full range of project activities.

Could you suggest any additional topic?

4) On a scale from 0 (not relevant at all) to 10 (extremely relevant), please rate the four pillars of our ethical principles when communicating to policymakers:

- Legal Background and Further Regulation.
- General Ethical Principles in the DEQ Grant Agreement.
- Compliance with EU Transparency Register.
- Complementary ethical principles to be applied.

Could you suggest any additional principle?

5) On a scale from 0 (not relevant at all) to 10 (extremely relevant), please rate the following better regulation requirements for communication with policymakers.

- To remove obstacles and red tape that slow down investments.
- To implement a 'one in, one out' approach to minimise regulatory burden for citizens and businesses.
- To mainstream the Sustainable Development Goals of the UN.

Could you suggest any additional requirement?

6) On a scale from 0 (not relevant at all) to 10 (extremely relevant), please rate the pillars of our political and regulatory framework with policymakers:

- Green Deal and 2030 climate framework.
- EU principles for sustainable raw materials.
- UN Sustainable Development Goals.

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- EU digital policies.
- H&S regulations.

Could you suggest any additional political and regulatory framework?

7) In your opinion, what strategy would be the most effective to improve communication with policymakers? (please clarify).

8) On a scale from 0 (not useful at all) to 10 (extremely useful), please rate the following options to interact with policymakers:

- Periodic and recurrent communication delivery. (Dissemination of project materials).
- Specific communication according to needs. (Case by case communication).
- Direct interaction. (Meetings and policy briefings).
- Direct interaction. (Enquiries & surveys).
- Direct interaction. (Workshops/seminars/conferences).
- Other (please specify).

Could you suggest any additional option?

9) In your opinion, how may we encourage aggregates' industry companies to use the project's products, developments and technologies?

- Through their national aggregates associations.
- Through UEPG & GAIN.
- Through technical media.
- Through workshops.
- Other (please specify).

10) In your opinion, what are the project's strengths in relation to the industry? (please limit the number to three).

11) In your opinion, what are the project's weaknesses in relation to the industry? (please limit the number to three).

12) On a scale from 0 (not aligned at all) to 10 (extremely aligned), please, rate how much the project's objectives are aligned with the extractive industry's ones.

13) In your opinion, may the industry employees reject using new technologies such as digitisation and AI? Please, rate from 0 (no rejection) to 10 (rejection).

14) In your opinion, may the use of new technologies, such as digitisation and AI, cause new risks for the mining industry workers? Please, rate from 0 (no new risks) to 10 (relevant new risks).

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15) Now that you know more about the project, how can we achieve international dissemination? (Please specify).

16) Now that you know more about the project, do you have any further proposals for our exploitation business plan? (Please specify).

3 Social acceptance survey

- 1) How relevant is social acceptance for extractive industries?
 - Not important.
 - Slightly important.
 - Moderately important.
 - Quite important.
 - Extremely important.

- 2) Which is the current level of social acceptance? In general, would you say the extractive industry is more accepted?
 - Not accepted at all.
 - Slightly accepted.
 - Moderately accepted.
 - Mostly accepted.
 - Completely accepted.

- 3) What are the main barriers to gaining social acceptance?
 - Competing for land resources.
 - Pollute air, land and water.
 - Visual impact.
 - Exposing workers to risks of fatal accidents, injuries and physical and mental health problems.
 - Exposing mining-affected communities to health and safety risks.
 - Other (write):

- 4) Any other barrier that are relevant, and why? (Write)

- 5) What kind of actions can be taken to address the barriers you have identified? Which are the most effective? (Select the four you consider most effective)
 - Preparing dedicated leaflets with information.
 - Having open door events.
 - Preparing a dedicated dossier with information.
 - Having meetings and site visits with the City Council.
 - Publishing News in local/regional media.
 - Sending newsletters/mailings.
 - Use of social media.

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- Use of websites.
 - Having a contact person.
 - Having a mailbox for suggestions.
 - Other (write):
- 6) Would you like to highlight any good practices to communicate and interact with local authorities and communities? (Write)
- 7) What is your opinion on the concept of social license to operate? Is it a useful tool?
- Yes, it's useful - I strongly believe that social license to operate is a valuable tool that companies should use to ensure they are operating in a socially responsible manner.
 - Yes, it's useful, but it shouldn't be mandatory.
 - No, it's not useful.
 - No, it's not useful and it could create conflicts.
 - Other (write):
- 8) In your experience, what are some of the key factors that contribute to employee acceptance of digitalization and procedure changes? (Select)
- Effective communication of the changes.
 - Providing adequate training and education.
 - Having leadership support.
 - Involving employees in the planning process.
 - Introducing changes in a way that minimizes disruption.
 - Recognizing and rewarding employees.
 - Perceiving the benefits.
 - Others (write):
- 9) What are the biggest barriers to gain the employees acceptance of digitalization and procedure changes? (Select)
- Resistance to change.
 - Lack of understanding of the changes and their benefits.
 - Lack of Training and education.
 - Low digital skills.
 - Culture and values of the organization.
 - Poor Communication of the changes.
 - Others (write):

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10) How can organizations improve their efforts to engage with and support their workers? (Select)

- Internal communication: giving regular updates.
- Having a bi-directional communication channel.
- Involving workers in decision-making.
- Development of communication material.
- Providing training.
- Others (write):

11) Do you know any good practice in the sector to upskill and reskill employees, particularly as new technologies and practices continue to emerge? (Write)

4 Dissemination and communication survey

- 1) Could you please write the official webpage(s) of your organisation?
- 2) Does your organisation use any of these social media?
 - LinkedIn.
 - Twitter.
 - Instagram.
 - YouTube.
- 3) Does your organisation post just about it or does it also share information about related initiatives?
 - Only about my organisation.
 - About other initiatives too.
- 4) Does your organisation have a newsletter?
 - Yes.
 - No.
- 5) If yes, would it be possible to send you articles about the project and publish them?
 - Yes.
 - No.
- 6) Does your company hold any events in which we could present our project?
 - Yes.
 - No.
- 7) If yes, please indicate the name of the event.
- 8) We would like to establish a solid communication with your organisation. If you think you might have any idea or field in which we could collaborate and work together, please let us know.

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